

Seed drill for upland rice grown in undulating terrain

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We tested four seed drills and two other conventional seeding practices (see table) for upland rice during three wet seasons (1995-97) in a randomized block design with three replications.

The soil was a lateritic, coarse-textured, well-drained sandy loam with pH 5.2, 0.03% total N, 20 kg available P ha⁻¹, 220 kg available K ha⁻¹, 13.1% field capacity, and 9.5% wilting point by weight basis. Rice variety Heera (85 d duration) was dry-seeded at 75 kg seeds ha⁻¹ with 60-30-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹. All P and K and 25% N were applied at sowing; 50% N was topdressed 20 d after sowing (DAS), with 25% N at 40 DAS.

Data on average depth of seed placement, seed population m², energy used for seeding, and grain yield are given in the table.

The highest rice grain yield (2.5 t ha⁻¹) was observed using T2 (Gujarat State Fertilizer Corporation seed-cum-fertilizer drill) (see figure). Broadcasting (T6) had the lowest yield (1.5 t ha⁻¹) and the highest energy requirement (360 MJ ha⁻¹) during seeding. The shallow seed depth resulted in poor crop stand.

Performance parameters of seed drills.

Treatment	Seed placement depth (cm)	Seed population m ² (no.)	Av yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Energy use (MJ ha ⁻¹)
T1-Implement factory seed drill (3-row, hand-drawn)	2.83	210	2.1	66.7
T2-Gujarat State Fertilizer Corp. seed-cum-fertilizer drill (2-row, bullock-drawn)	2.65	233	2.5	266.4
T3-Implement factory seed drill (1-row, bullock-drawn)	2.15	196	2.2	374.6
T4-Annapurna seed drill (5-row, hand-drawn)	1.22	173	2.3	378.4
T5-Sowing behind the plow	2.17	179	1.9	121.5
T6-Broadcasting	1.30	125	1.5	360.0

Note: Seed rate was 75 kg ha⁻¹ for all treatments.

The Gujarat State Fertilizer Corporation seed-cum-fertilizer drill.

Rolling marker for a rice field

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Ninety-five percent of rice farmers in South Sulawesi, Indonesia, transplant rice using a traditional marker called a *caplak*. The marker is shaped and works like a traditional harrow. When it is pulled forward, it leaves straight-line marks on the soil. The

marker should then be pulled again at right angles to mark the planting row.

A new rolling marker (see figure) was designed which, in contrast to the traditional system, will indicate the points for planting when pulled only once. Straight

lines are made by the wheels and cross lines are made by the outer beams.

To simplify the tool, wheel circumference was fixed at 100 cm. Each wheel was then divided by 4 or 5 to give a distance of 25 or 20 cm. The six wheels are